

Assessment of Background Noise Levels in Four Commercial Areas of Freetown, Sierra Leone

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ABSTRACT:

Environmental noise is a significant public health issue, particularly in rapidly urbanizing cities where commercial activities contribute to elevated noise pollution. Despite its numerous implications, few studies have focused on noise levels in commercial environments in developing countries. This study aims to fill this existing gap by assessing background noise levels in four commercial areas of Freetown, Sierra Leone: Aberdeen Market, Godrich Street, Jui Junction, and Sani Abacha Street. Using a calibrated handheld sound level meter, measurements were taken during daytime, evening, and nighttime periods over one week. Noise levels were analyzed using the day-evening-night equivalent continuous noise level (Lden) and statistical methods to assess compliance with World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines. Results revealed that all areas exhibit average noise levels above the WHO recommended limit of 70 dBA during daytime and evening hours, with Godrich Street and Aberdeen Market exhibiting the highest average daytime noise level (95.35 dBA) and the lowest average nighttime noise level (53.05 dBA) respectively. Godrich Street recorded the highest Lden value and shortest allowed exposure of 93.34 dBA and 1.17 hours respectively, indicating the most significant risk of prolonged exposure. Recommendations include creating designated quiet zones tailored to local commercial layouts, stricter enforcement of noise regulations, public awareness campaigns on hearing protection, and

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regular noise monitoring to guide urban planning. This study provides crucial insights for mitigating noise pollution and improving urban sustainability in developing nations.

Keywords: Environmental noise, Business environment, Equivalent continuous noise level, Allowed exposure.

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INTRODUCTION

Noise pollution, characterized by excessive and disruptive sound, is a pervasive environmental issue with significant public health implications [1]. Globally, rapid urbanization and industrialization have intensified environmental noise levels, particularly in developing countries, where weak regulatory frameworks and high population densities exacerbate the problem [2, 3]. Environmental noise arising from sources such as motor vehicles, industrial activities, street vendors, and public gatherings, contributes to stress, sleep disturbances, cardiovascular diseases, hearing loss, and cognitive decline [4, 5, 6, 7]. Recognizing these risks, the World Health Organization established a 24-hour equivalent sound level (L_{Aeq}) limit of 70 dBA for commercial environments, beyond which noise exposure poses severe health threats [8]. Despite these guidelines, noise levels in urban environments, particularly in developing regions, frequently exceed permissible thresholds, leading to adverse health outcomes and diminished quality of life [9].

Studies in other developing countries highlight the widespread impacts of noise pollution. In Nigeria, noise levels in schools, markets, and workshops consistently exceeded regulatory limits, adversely affecting quality of life [10]. Similarly, research in Malaysia demonstrated that commercial and traffic noise significantly disrupted daily activities and public health [11]. However, these studies often focus on broad urban environments, overlooking the distinct dynamics of commercial hubs in rapidly urbanizing cities. Freetown, the capital and largest city in Sierra Leone, exemplifies these challenges, with its unregulated urban expansion, high population density, and diverse noise sources, including makeshift generators and congested traffic [12]. These conditions create a particularly challenging acoustic environment, yet empirical data on background noise levels in Freetown's commercial areas remain scarce, hindering effective noise management and urban planning.

Localized assessments from other regions underscore the importance of targeted strategies to address noise pollution. For instance, studies in Haridwar City, India, revealed that unregulated urban environments foster excessive noise pollution and necessitate tailored interventions [13]. Similarly, research in Chidambaram Town, India, emphasized community-specific mitigation measures to address unique noise challenges [14]. These findings highlight the need for context-sensitive strategies, particularly in Freetown, where the prevalence of street vendors using loudspeakers, limited enforcement of noise regulations, and inadequate urban planning exacerbate the problem. This study seeks to address these gaps by systematically assessing background noise levels in four major commercial areas of Freetown: Aberdeen Market, Godrich Street, Jui Junction, and Sani Abacha Street. By focusing on these unique commercial environments, the research provides actionable insights into how noise pollution impacts Freetown's urban landscape and offers evidence-based recommendations. The findings aim to inform urban planning, enhance public health policies, and contribute to the development of sustainable noise control frameworks, not only for Freetown but also for other rapidly urbanizing cities in developing countries.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study was conducted within four major commercial areas (Aberdeen Market, Godrich Street, Jui Junction and Sani Abacha Street) of Freetown, Sierra Leone. Freetown serves as the administrative, financial and commercial center of the country and is characterized by diverse commercial activities that contribute to varying levels of environmental noise. The study areas were selected based on their commercial activities and population densities. Aberdeen Market is located in the western part of Freetown and is on latitude 8.482° N and longitude -13.267° W, Godrich street is located in the eastern part of Freetown and has geographical coordinates of latitude 8.433° N and longitude 13.283° W, Jui junction is situated in the eastern part of Freetown and has coordinates 8.4131° N latitude and 13.1310° W longitude, and Sani Abacha Street is located in the eastern part of Freetown and on 11.9932° N latitude and 8.5242° W longitude. Sierra Leone is located on the Atlantic coast on latitude $8^{\circ} 29' 24''$ N and longitude $13^{\circ} 14' 3''$ W.

Figure 1. Map showing Freetown, Sierra Leone

Noise Measurements

To assess the noise levels in the four selected commercial business environments in Freetown, noise measurements were conducted using a calibrated handheld digital sound level meter (DSM8930), specifically designed for environmental noise monitoring with a measurement range of (40-130) dBA, an accuracy of ± 2 dBA, and a resolution of 0.1 dBA, powered by a 9V battery. Figure 2 show the digital sound level meter that was used for data collections.

Figure 2. Handheld Digital Sound Level Meter

The two weighting networks that are used to measure sounds are the A and C networks. The A-weighting network (dBA) is however used for assessments of environmental noise because it approximates how the human ear perceives sound levels [15]. Hence, the digital sound level meter was calibrated and set with an A-weighted frequency response and a slow time response, held at a height of 1.2 meters above ground level, approximately 10 meters away from any building and at least 3.5 meters from any reflecting surface other than the ground.

For measuring the background noise level at the four locations, times of the day were divided into the following periods: daytime (7:00 a.m. to 7:00 p.m.), evening (7:00 p.m. to 11:00 p.m.), and nighttime (11:00 p.m. to 7:00 a.m. the following day). Ten noise level measurements were taken, recorded, and averaged during each defined interval (daytime, evening, and nighttime) at each location. Data collection lasted for a week, and the average noise levels were compiled in a Microsoft Excel sheet to determine the equivalent continuous noise levels (L_{Aeq}) and the allowed exposure for each commercial business area. The equivalent continuous noise levels were determined using the day-evening-night equivalent continuous noise level (L_{den}) equation, which imposes a penalty on sound levels during the evening and night. This equation is given by [16]:

$$L_{den} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{1}{24} (12 \times 10^{\frac{L_{day}}{10}} + 4 \times 10^{\frac{L_{evening}+5}{10}} + 8 \times 10^{\frac{L_{night}+10}{10}}) \quad (1)$$

It is primarily used for noise assessments of airports, busy main roads, main railway lines and in cities over 100,000 residents [17].

The allowed exposure periods in hours were estimated for commercial business areas using the following equation [18]:

$$T = \frac{8}{2^{\frac{(L-85)}{3}}} \quad (2)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the average noise levels (L_{Aeq}) for each defined period (daytime, evening and nighttime), the mean L_{Aeq} , the minimum and maximum L_{Aeq} and the continuous noise levels (L_{den}) at each commercial business area.

Table 1. Noise Levels in Four Selected Commercial Business Areas in Freetown

Commercial business area	Average noise level (L_{Aeq}) in dBA							Allowed Exposure in hr
	Daytime	Evening	Nighttime	Mean	Min. L_{Aeq}	Max. L_{Aeq}	L_{den}	
Aberdeen Market	85.72	77.55	53.05	72.11	53.05	85.72	83.37	11.66
Godrich Street	95.35	89.15	63.92	82.81	63.92	95.35	93.34	1.17
Jui Junction	85.32	84.4	72.68	80.80	72.68	85.32	85.77	6.70
Sani Abacha Street	89.12	85.8	63.74	79.55	63.74	89.12	87.90	4.09

All average noise levels observed during daytime and evening hours exceeded the recommended WHO limit of 70 dBA for commercial environments and with the exemption of night-time average noise level at Jui junction, all night-time average noise levels fall below the limit. The maximum average noise level of 95.35 dBA was recorded during day-time at Godrich Street and the minimum average noise level of 53.05 dBA was recorded during night-time at Aberdeen market. This is illustrated in Figure 3 below.

The mean daily average noise levels for all commercial business areas were also observed to exceed the limit with Aberdeen market and Godrich Street recording the minimum and maximum values of

72.11 dBA and 82.81 dBA respectively. Also, the equivalent continuous noise levels (L_{den}) for all four commercial business areas were observed to significantly exceed the limit with Aberdeen Market and Godrich Street having the minimum and maximum L_{den} values of 83.37 dBA and 93.34 dBA respectively. This is represented in Figure 4 below.

Figure 3. Average Noise Levels at Commercial Business Areas

Figure 4. Mean Daily Average and Equivalent Continuous Noise Levels

Figure 4 shows the allowed exposure period to noise at the various locations. The longest and shortest allowed exposure periods of 11.66 hrs and 1.17 hr were observed at Aberdeen market and Godrich Street respectively.

Figure 5. Allowed Exposure Periods within Commercial Business Areas

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that noise pollution in commercial areas of Freetown, Sierra Leone, exceeds acceptable levels established by the World Health Organization. With high noise levels recorded in prominent commercial areas, especially Godrich Street, the health risks associated with prolonged exposure become a significant public health concern. Effective noise management strategies must be implemented to safeguard the well-being of workers, residents, and visitors in these commercial areas.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The authors recommend the following:

1. Regulatory authorities should enforce noise control regulations to limit excessive noise in commercial areas, with stricter penalties for non-compliance to incentivize businesses and street vendors to adopt quieter practices.
2. Implement educational campaigns to inform traders, residents, and the public about the health risks of extended exposure to high noise levels, emphasizing the importance of using protective measures like earplugs.
3. Regular noise assessments should be conducted in commercial areas to monitor changes over time.
4. Explore the possibility of installing noise barriers or enhancing sound insulation in affected buildings to provide relief for those frequently affected by high noise levels.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

M.M.A. designed the study, F.K.J., M.S., M.J., A.S., A.M.A., and M.M.S coordinated the data collection. All authors contributed to the study design and manuscript preparation, M.M.A. contributed to the data analyses, and was lead author of the manuscript. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data supporting this article have been included in the article.

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